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VIRAL MARKETING – A POWER TOOL FOR E-MARKETING

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INTRODUCTION:

One of the latest buzzwords in e-commerce is "viral marketing" - the basic idea being to use the power of the Internet to spread the good news about a product like an epidemic. The concept of viral marketing is not new. Its precursor Word-of-mouth marketing has been around for ages. The principle behind word-of-mouth marketing is simple; use influencers to generate peer-to-peer product recommendations. Prior to the advent of the Internet, however, this form of marketing was too disjointed to effectively benefit most advertisers. The effect of word-of-mouth was largely confined to specific geographic areas simply due to the lack of widespread social networks. Word-of-mouth was generally limited by the ability of the influencer to effectively speak to another prospective customer, hence the term "word-of-mouth".

The Internet has radically changed the concept of word-of-mouth, so much so that the term "viral marketing" was coined by venture capitalist Steve Jurvetson in 1997. The term was used to describe Hotmail's email practice of appending advertising for themselves to outgoing mail from their users. The assumption is that if such an advertisement reaches a "susceptible" user, that user will become "infected" (i.e., sign up for an account) and can then go on to infect other susceptible users. While e-mail may have been the original catalyst; the advent of social networks, online communities and chat provide the ability to distribute information exponentially faster than ever before. The spread of an effective viral marketing campaign is akin to an epidemic outbreak of a virus, limited only by the potency and relevance of the marketing message.

WHAT IS VIRAL MARKETING?

On the Internet, viral marketing is any marketing technique that induces Websites or users to pass on a marketing message to other sites or users, creating a potentially exponential growth in the message's visibility and effect. The phenomenon is also known by many other names such as:

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Avalanche marketing• Organic marketing• Buzz marketing• Propagation marketing• Cascading style marketing• Grass root marketing• Wildfire marketing	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Referral marketing• Centrifugal marketing• Ripple marketing• Exponential marketing• Self perpetuation marketing• Fission marketing• Self propagation marketing
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First, it is relevant to answer the question what (online) viral marketing actually is by drawing upon some scientific and non-scientific literature. The Wikipedia defines viral marketing as "marketing techniques that seek to exploit pre-existing social networks to produce exponential increase in brand awareness, through viral processes similar to the spread of an epidemic. It is word-of-mouth delivered and enhanced online; it harnesses the network effect of the Internet and can be very useful in reaching a large number of people rapidly. In his book *The Anatomy of Buzz: How to Create Word-Of-Mouth Marketing* (2002), Emmanuel Rosen claim that viral marketing is best described as a "pass-it-on promotion" or "tell-a-friend promotion" which is used by customers within a

commercial market in order to "produce information instantly and spread it to dozens or even thousands of others". This definition indicates that viral marketing is used within the commercial sector and that it is between consumers. Internet marketing consultant Kim Brooks agrees with Rosens' definition of viral marketing, but adds that 'customers' usually are aware of the fact that they are 'telling a friend' and that viral marketing can be found in our daily lives as well as online. Therefore, Brooks claims that viral marketing is "a form of motivated word of mouth that works offline as well as online". Just like Rosen's definition, this one indicates that viral-marketing is about communication between consumers as well.

Steve Jurvetson and Tim Draper explain the above named online functioning of viral marketing by examining www.hotmail.com. While doing this, they keep in mind their definition of viral marketing: "a pattern of rapid adoption through word-of-mouth networks". By networks, they mean groups of people giving attention to the online advertisement made by "new companies" which "structure their businesses in a way that allows them to grow like a virus ...". By saying this, they indicate that viral marketing is a strategy that is dependant of word-of-mouth communication between consumers as well. They explain why viral marketing carries the word "viral" at the same time. This is also done by Jeffrey Boase and Barry Wellman (2001), who take the explanation of the term 'viral' a step further by claiming that viral marketing has some similarities with biological viruses (such as the possibility to 'catch' a virus and the rapid spreading of the viruses), which is an interesting comparison but goes a bit too far, since a human being and a marketing strategy are quite different things.

Dr. Ralph F. Wilson, an e-commerce consultant and director of the magazine *Web Marketing Today*, offers a broader definition which covers all definitions above, although he does not make a distinction between online and offline viral marketing like Brooks does. According to Wilson, viral marketing is "any strategy that encourages individuals to pass on a marketing message to others, creating the potential for exponential growth in the message's exposure and influence". Noteworthy is the fact that Wilson stresses the message's influence and thereby talks about the message itself in his definition, while other definitions named above are mainly about communication between consumers. The definitions above also seem to lack in mentioning involvement of businesses when communicating with businesses' audiences as well, which is an important element of viral marketing.

Sandeep Krishnamurthy, Professor of Marketing at the University of Washington, is interested in all aspects of e-marketing, especially in Internet advertising and promotion. His definition adds that online viral marketing works "through customer-to-customer communication rather than firm-to-customer communication", which indicates that viral marketing is a "technique for building customer traffic on the Internet, leveraging customer networks to build traffic" used by companies using the Internet to promote their products. Or, as the author puts it, "viral marketing proposes that messages can be rapidly disseminated from consumer to consumer leading to large-scale market acceptance".

Comparable to Rosens' "pass-it-on promotion" or "tell-a-friend promotion", Krishnamurthy calls viral marketing a "send-this-story-to-your-friend" strategy. In brief: it can be said that viral marketing is a marketing technique used by companies to attract consumers. Messages (usually advertisements) created by these companies are passed on by consumers without interference of these companies (which means that viral marketing uses word-of-mouth communication). Messages will get known by a lot of people this way, which makes it inviting for companies to use this strategy. Viral marketing works offline as well as online.

WHY VIRAL MARKETING?

The proliferation of marketing and advertising, coupled with the onslaught of millions of media channels in today's world, has given cause for consumers to screen out and effectively avoid a great

deal of traditional supplier driven messaging. Most of the traditional media channels are facing increasing competition for effectively capturing the viewer's attention and provide positive ROI for the marketer.

This competition, coupled with the rising cost of media buys, has caused marketers to search for an alternative means to reach the customer in an effective manner. Viral marketing is an attractive solution because it utilizes the free endorsement of the individual rather than purchase of mass media to spread the word. Because the distribution model is free, viral communication can potentially be lower cost and more effective than traditional media.

THE VIRAL EFFECT

It is a fact that majority of Internet users often share information with friends, family and associates. According to Jupiter Research more than 90% of consumers tell at least one other person about a Web site when the original recommendation came from a friend.

According to a report released by the marketing agency Sharpe Partners 89% of US adult Internet users share content with friends, family and associates by e-mail, and they do so often. Key findings of the report:

- Frequency of sharing content
 - o 63% share content at least once a week
 - o 25% share daily or almost daily.
- Number of people with whom they share
 - o 75% shares with more than one person
- Content
 - o 88% jokes and cartoons
 - o 56% news
 - o 24% business and personal finance
- Branded content for companies looking to employ a viral marketing program:
 - o Over 40% said they are more or slightly more likely to send marketing-related 1 messages
 - o Only 5% refuse to share content that contains a clear brand message.

VIRAL MARKETING IN ACTION

Now, having understood what viral marketing is, who uses it and what it is used for, let's take a look at the basic functioning of viral marketing. As mentioned before, Krishnamurthy stresses the functioning of viral marketing through "customer-to-customer communication than firm-to-customer communication". He claims that this element of viral marketing makes this technique successful, since "individuals are more likely to accept the recommendations of their friends" than of companies, which makes it more probable for companies that their messages actually get read. Or, as the author puts it: "a friend is likely to be a better predictor of an individual's taste as opposed to a firm that does not know a given personality", the fact that consumers' "choices and purchase decisions" can be influenced by "personal influence" and "informal exchange of information" was already proved in the 1950s and is still used for audience targeting.

Viral marketing's advantage to traditional ways of advertising (advertisements in print or on TV, for instance) is the fact that on the one hand messages are better targeted since people within a

network know what other people in the network need and considered to be unbiased because of its source on the other. Unlike traditional advertising Viral is not an interruptive technique and is often welcomed by the receiver irrespective of the fact whether ultimately they like it or not. Marketing researchers for Harvard Business Online Michael J. Robert and Shripriya Mahesh confirm this by claiming that viral marketing functions best within these networks since people within these groups have shared interests. It's the fact that viral marketing works through networks of consumers (friends, colleagues et cetera) that makes viral marketing strong in building and sustaining customer traffic, which usually is a hard thing to do online, since there are many web sites trying to attract people's attention.

Krishnamurthy distinguishes three forms of viral marketing:

1. Incidental contagion: In which "the consumer is not explicitly made aware of his or her role in the message dissemination process". Hotmail is a good example of this strategy, since every e-mail message sent out by Hotmail has a tag line at the bottom saying "Get Your Private, Free Email at <http://www.hotmail.com>", which makes people sign up rapidly and saves Hotmail a lot of advertisement costs.
2. Contagion due to transaction consummation: In which "a service is available to individual only if others (ranging from one other person to many others) sign up". An example of this strategy is the chat program ICQ, which makes people download the program before being able to chat with people online.
3. Consumers as professional recruiters: In which "consumers are encouraged to contact others and inform them about the product". Examples are buttons next to online journal articles saying "tell a friend".

Krishnamurthy admits that spreading messages online via viral marketing can be unpredictable since "all individuals are not created equal" (some people are more curious than others and some have a "greater need to spread market information" than others), but claim that the functioning of viral marketing is proven in spite of these rather small unpredictabilities.

Rosen agrees with Krishnamurthy about the low advertisement costs that viral marketing comes along with. Viral marketing is just about "spreading the word and then letting it grow". He stresses that brand-name recognition is a requisite for the functioning of viral marketing, since brand names are the thing that people need to remember when sending a message to friends.

Brooks agrees with Rosen and adds three other requisites needed by viral marketing in order to succeed:

1. Really valuable service or content ("natural word of mouth");
2. Bribery ("in the form of contests or kickback schemes");
3. Entertainment ("animations, postcards, et cetera").

Although not explaining too deeply what she means by these requisites, it may be obvious that viral marketing is about more than just about making people spread a message. In order to prove this, Brooks gives some useful examples of and solutions to pitfalls for companies when using online viral marketing, such as "associations with negative sites or people" and "breaking netiquette such as spamming". When using viral marketing, companies should still create strong brand names and identities and "keep the spread of the virus properly valued, paced and targeted".

Wilson (2000) confirms this statement by claiming that not all viral marketing strategies work as good and, just like Brooks, mentions some useful elements that companies can include in a viral marketing strategy in order to succeed:

1. Giving away products or services (such as "free e-mail services, free software programs, free buttons");
2. Providing for effortless transfer to others ("short is better": marketing messages should be short, so that they can be remembered better);
3. Scaling easily from small to very large (in terms of "server space, bandwidth, support staff, fulfillment etc");
4. Exploiting common motivations and behaviors (appealing to people's needs);
5. Utilizing existing communication networks ("placing messages between existing networks between people");
6. Taking advantage of others' resources (online news releases or entries on web logs can provide companies with useful information for marketers).

However the fact is that every viral marketing strategy should be attributed to the specific product the campaign is designed for. This view is also shared by Kevin Fitzpatrick (2003), who claims that one of the most effective ways to reach a target audience is "to utilize a viral marketing campaign that is specific to your audience and ties in to your offering". According to James Kydd, Brand Director of Virgin Mobile, "Viral Marketing is not used as a one-off tactical end in itself, but as an integrated strategic part of the overall marketing mix. It is a means to an end whereby it not only generates buzz, but also provides ongoing, quantifiable brand benefits, such as increased awareness, peer-to-peer endorsement and ultimately more sales. "Speaking of viral marketing strategies, Juvetson and Draper explain in their article "Viral Marketing" that the Internet makes it possible for advertisements to spread and for companies to grow rapidly; but companies should still keep in mind customer retention.

"Seeding" the original message is a key component of a viral campaign. Seeding is the act of planting the campaign with the initial group who will then go on to spread the campaign to others. The Internet provides a wide array of options for seeding, including: E-mail, Online Forums (Google, Yahoo groups), Social Networks (orkut.com, MySpace.com, Facebook.com), Instant Messengers (Yahoo, ICQ, MSN, Google, India Times, Rediff etc), Blogs, Pod casts etc. When determining where to seed it is important that marketers should take into consideration the audience targeted. Failure to do so may kill a campaign before it ever gets off the ground. Although all sources mentioned above speak rather positive about online viral marketing, the functioning of online viral marketing brings along some questions, as well. An article at www.applesforhealth.com written by an unknown author says that some forms, of Internet advertising do not seem to work very well. A research at the University of Southern California's Marshall School of Business, proved that only 11 of 100 students exposed to an online advertisement banner remembered the banner itself: Still, although "click-rates were low", 62 percent of all students were able to name the brand the banner had on it. It was concluded that "awareness is more important than click-through".

SOME EXAMPLES:

www.Hotmail.com

One of the most successful viral marketing campaigns of all time was the viral marketing strategy Hotmail used for its free e-mail web site <http://www.hotmail.com> in which a simple text advertisement appended to each users email. The free e-mail service spent a mere: \$50,000 on traditional marketing and still became the world's 1eading e-mail provider almost overnight, with 75 million users. According to Krishnamurthy, Hotmail is a form of incidental contagion. This means that users are usually "not aware of his or her role in the message dissemination process": as a Hotmail user, you sign in on the web site wanting to read or send e-mail, not being fully aware of the

fact that you are in fact performing a promotional task by doing so. In fact, you are, since every e-mail message sent out by Hotmail has a tag line at the bottom saying "Get Your Private, Free Email at <http://www.hotmail.com>". Also, when people see or write down your e-mail address, they will remember the word 'Hotmail' in it. During the first 18 months, Krishnamurthy says, more than 12 million people signed up to get their own Hotmail account. This made it possible for Hotmail to cut down on promotion costs. According to <http://www.viralmarketer.com> advertising, marketing and promotion costs were very low, and even without marketing in India, Hotmail is one of the largest email provider in India nowadays.

Jurvetson & Draper (1998) add that Hotmail also succeeds in attracting people because of the fact that "every Hotmail subscriber had filled out a detailed demographic and psychographic profile including occupation and salary", which offers Hotmail marketers a lot of personal information free that can be used to define and address targeted audiences.

DeBeers: DeBeers gave website consumers the opportunity to design their own rings and then share their designs with family and friends. DeBeers found visitors enjoyed the site and did actually share it with others.

Gap: San Francisco retailer Gap Inc. recently added a viral ad to its promotional mix with the addition of a virtual model. The virtual model lets viewers create an image and select physical traits including weight, skin tone, and hair. Consumers can then choose various outfits for the model to wear and club music will play as model performs a striptease down to his or her undergarments before going to the dressing room.

Volvo: Volvo is a brand known for safe and reliable vehicles and so experimenting with viral marketing was considered particularly innovative for a typically conservative company. They used the web to launch an entry-level luxury S40 by presenting a story set in a small town in Sweden where 32 people bought new S40s in one day. They went so far to include a documentary about the event as well as information on the "film director", Carlos Settle. The S40 became a top-seller for Volvo.

Trojan Games: The Trojan Games viral marketing campaign (www.trojangames.co.uk), with its award-winning sex and games spoof video content, has been seen by over 38 million people globally since the launch of site in October 2003. In its first month alone, over 6 million people visited the site. Only sites such as Google and Yahoo reach more people over such a time period. The following brand benefits were revealed in a consumer survey:

- 77% recalled the Trojan brand after seeing the campaign
- 73% positive rating of the overall impression of the campaign
- 80% perceived the campaign to be unique
- 50% would be more likely to consider the Trojan brand after seeing the campaign

CONCLUDING REMARKS

In brief, it can be said that viral marketing is an important and powerful tool in e-marketing which works through customer-to-customer communication rather than through firm-to-customer communication, so that customers' tastes are more easily influenced and targeted audiences are reached better. In order to be successful, viral marketing should not only include proper seeding and rapid spreading of messages, but other elements as well, such as giving away products or services, strong brand names and utilizing existing communication networks. Viral marketing is a credible marketing tactic that can deliver positive ROI when properly executed as a component of an overarching strategic plan. Marketers should utilize viral marketing when the messaging can coincide and support a measurable business goal.

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